

RISK MANAGEMENT AND PERFORMANCE OF CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS IN LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Objective of the study: This study examined the impact of resource and budget control risk management on the cost of housing projects in Lagos State, Nigeria, using empirical data from low-, medium--, and high-priced projects.

Research Methods/Methodology: The study adopted a mixed-methods approach using purposive sampling to select 120 participants. Data was collected through an interview guide and a questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics with SPSS and thematic analysis with N Vivo software.

Originality/Value: This study is original and valuable as it applies the resource dependency and limits theories to investigate the success or failure of housing projects in Lagos State, Nigeria. It also provides insights into the challenges, methods, benefits, and suggestions for resource and budget control risk management in different housing projects.

Managerial/Practical implication: The findings of this study have implications for policy, practice, theory, and future research. They suggest that resource and budget control risk management are significant predictors of the cost of housing projects and that the cost varies depending on the type and location of the project. They also highlight the need for effective resource planning, allocation, monitoring, cost management, and material allocation.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the British Standard (2000), as referenced by Kariuki et al. (2018), a project can be defined as the deliberate and systematic execution of a predetermined set of actions, meticulously planned and coordinated, with a clearly defined commencement and conclusion,

aimed at achieving specific goals and objectives within predetermined limitations. The economic progress of nations is contingent upon their capacity to successfully execute a diverse range of significant initiatives that contribute towards realizing their long-term goals. Governments in both developing and affluent nations employ various initiatives to enhance the quality of life for their respective populations.

Creating new infrastructure and structures substantially fosters economic growth (Mariusz et al., 2019). According to (Ong'ondo, Gwaya, et al. 2019), Nigeria's federal and state governments have allocated significant financial resources towards public building initiatives to enhance the quality of life for the country's populace. CORBON, the Council of Registered Builders of Nigeria, is a corporate organization authorized by Section 2 of the legislation to establish standards for the building industry in Nigeria. CORBON's principal goal is to regulate and manage the application of Building technology across the board (DemaMunef et al., 2023).

Lagos State is renowned for its high population density and significant economic prosperity within the Nigerian context. The government has initiated several large-scale construction projects to cater to its population. Several of these programs, however, have encountered challenges such as delays, exceeding budgetary limits, subpar quality, and discontent among stakeholders. According to the (Lagos State Government 2023), just nine out of the thirty-two building projects initiated between 2014 and 2019 were completed. The challenges above have impeded the progress and growth of the state.

Insufficient risk management is a significant factor contributing to the suboptimal performance of construction projects (Gyamfiet, al 2018). Risks refer to events or situations characterized by uncertainty, which have the potential to either facilitate or impede the advancement of a project (Sharma & Gupta, 2021). The identification, assessment, evaluation, and mitigation of project hazards are accomplished through risk management. Project success may be measured by factors such as enhanced stakeholder satisfaction, optimal allocation of resources, mitigation of risks, and successful project completion, all of which can be facilitated by implementing efficient risk management strategies.

As one of Nigeria's most populous and active states, Lagos State relies heavily on the building sector to drive economic growth. However, many Lagos State housing projects experience delays, cost overruns, inferior quality, and dissatisfied stakeholders. These problems lessen the state's progress and development and lower living standards.

Inadequate risk management is a significant contributor to housing projects' underperformance. Uncertain occurrences or situations are risks that can either help or hinder the project's progress. Risk management identifies, assesses, evaluates, and counters project hazards. Project success may include increased stakeholder satisfaction, resource utilization, risk avoidance, and project completion via effective risk management.

Despite its importance, there needs to be more data showing how risk management affects the success of housing projects in Lagos State. Some researchers have tried to

figure out what makes a project successful, but they have yet to focus on the part risk management plays. Furthermore, these studies have largely ignored the specific opportunities and difficulties faced by housing developments in Lagos State and have focused on other locations or nations.

To help close that knowledge gap, this research will analyze how risk management affects the success of building projects in Lagos State. The study will examine the use of two distinct forms of risk management in low-, medium-, and high-priced housing projects: resource risk management and budget control risk management. One component of project performance, the cost of delivering housing projects, will be analyzed through these risk management strategies. Data will be gathered and analyzed using quantitative and qualitative techniques, such as surveys, interviews, and document analysis.

This research will add to the current project management literature by offering empirical insights into the connection between risk management and project performance. As an added benefit, the research will provide actionable ways for home construction projects in Lagos State to manage risk better. Project managers, builders, consultants, customers, regulators, and beneficiaries are some groups that stand to gain from this study. The research would also contribute to the state's development goals and vision by improving the efficacy and efficiency of Lagos State's housing projects.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study are.

- i. To examine the influence of resource risk management on the performance of housing projects in Lagos State, Nigeria
- ii. To assess the influence of budget control risk management on the cost of delivery of housing projects in Lagos State, Nigeria.

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

3.1 Risk Management in Construction Projects

It is crucial to closely monitor and plan for uncertain events or circumstances that can positively or negatively affect project objectives to reduce their influence (Naeem et al., 2018; Alsadi&Norhayatizakuan, 2021). Project managers must employ efficient risk management tactics to secure the punctual culmination of construction endeavours and the contentment of all involved parties. Nevertheless, there needs to be more empirical data about the impact of risk management on the performance of construction projects in Lagos State, Nigeria. It is important to note that this impact may vary depending on the specific area and kind of project being executed (Mishra &Moktan, 2019).

Lagos state is well recognized as a highly populated and economically thriving region within Nigeria. The area has initiated several large-scale construction projects to cater to its population. Issues about punctuality, financial constraints, standard adherence, and dissatisfied parties involved have marred numerous undertakings. These hurdles hinder the state's economic development and negatively impact the overall well-being of its population.

(Gyamfi, et. al. 2018) Assert that inadequate risk management is a prominent factor contributing to the failure of building projects. It is imperative to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the influence of risk management on the efficacy of construction projects in Lagos State. This study will primarily examine resource risk management and budget control risk management. Cash flow, materials, working capital, equipment, human resources, cost estimates, budgets, timelines, design modifications, procurement, and construction are all facets under management (ENISA, 2023).

3.2 Resource Risk Management

Risks associated with allocating and using project resources can be reduced via resource risk management techniques. "resources" describes various inputs and assets, including money, goods, machinery, people, and more. The success of risk management depends on the ability to recognize, analyze, and respond to potential dangers and rewards in terms of available resources and their influence on the project's goals. When resource risk management principles are applied, project managers may reap benefits, such as more efficient asset allocation and utilization. Consequently, this can lead to cost reduction, enhanced efficiency, increased production, and added value for all stakeholders.

The four stages of resource risk management are as follows:

- Forecasting possible resource risks. Risk variables like demand, supply, price, quality, quantity, etc., that may impact the availability of the resources needed for the project are identified and assessed at this stage.
- Risk assessment. At this stage, the evaluation of each risk in terms of how likely it is to occur and how much of an effect it may have on the project if it did. This phase also includes a risk registry and a ranking of hazards according to severity and urgency.
- Risk action plan. The next stage is to make a strategy to lessen the impact of potential dangers and maximize the benefits of possible openings. You are assigning tasks, providing resources, establishing timelines, and keeping tabs on the status of each risk response, which all fall under this category.
- Monitoring and control. As new or current risks evolve, tracking and evaluating how well the solutions have worked is essential. Part of this phase is informing those with a vested interest in the result of the risk management process.

3.3 Budget Control Risk Management

The effective management of risks related to budget control includes estimating, assigning, and monitoring the financial plan of a project. Cost overruns, underused resources, and missed deadlines can have severe consequences, which can be minimized or prevented by implementing effective risk management strategies focused on budget control (Seber, 2011). Project managers have several potential advantages in using risk management and budget control strategies. These benefits include optimizing resource use, enhancing project deliverables' overall value, and gaining suspicious stakeholders' trust and support (Naeem et al., 2018).

There are four phases of risk management in budget control:

- Forecasting possible budget risks. Market fluctuations, design modifications, scope creep, resource shortages, etc., are risks that might negatively impact a project's budget and must be pinpointed at this stage.
- Risk assessment. The next stage is assessing each risk's potential and financial impact. At this stage, you will also want to capture the hazards in a risk register and rank them according to severity and urgency.
- Risk action plan. The next stage is to make a strategy to lessen the impact of potential dangers and maximize the benefits of possible openings. You are assigning tasks, providing resources, establishing timelines, and keeping tabs on the status of each risk response, which all fall under this category.
- Monitoring and control. As new or current risks evolve, tracking and evaluating how well the solutions have worked is essential. Part of this phase is informing those with a vested interest in the result of the risk management process.

Project managers can increase their chances of success by paying attention to and actively managing the risks associated with the project's budget. Risk management for fiscal restraint calls for meticulous preparation, analysis, and implementation. Managers of projects should employ proper methods and resources to detect, evaluate, and counteract any financial threats. Managers of projects should have all relevant parties participate in and provide input for risk assessments(Alsaadi et al., 2021).

3.4 Theoretical Review

The resource dependency theory and the theory of constraints serve as theoretical anchors for this investigation. The success or failure of home construction projects in Lagos State, Nigeria, can be better understood in light of these ideas on resource risk management and budget control risk management.

3.5 Resource Dependence Theory

Pfeffer and Salancik put out the resource dependency theory (1978). It stresses that an organization's resources are essential to its continued existence and growth. However, these are typically hard to come by and compete for among other groups (Findikil,2019). That is why businesses must control their reliance on outside resources and take precautions against resource scarcity.

This theory posits that modern companies have a significant hurdle in resource unpredictability. It is contingent upon three variables: the availability, concentration, and interdependence of resources (Findikil, 2019). These aspects reveal how regulated, variable, and intricate the required assets are. To deal with the risks and benefits associated with the resources, it is crucial to implement efficient risk management solutions.

This theory's insights into resource risk dynamics and consequences in building projects make it applicable to our investigation. This hypothesis suggests that building projects in Lagos State face resource risk due to competition for scarce state resources from other projects. For instance, the Lagos State Government's budget for building projects is small and highly contended. This research aims to apply the resource

dependency theory to analyze the impact of resource risk management on the success of real estate development projects in Lagos State.

3.6 Theory of Constraints

Goldratt and Cox (1984) established the theory of constraints. It defines a limitation as limiting the potential benefits of a project or procedure. According to this theory, a system's efficiency is capped by its slowest part or bottleneck. Both internal and external factors act as restraints on a company's operations. Politics, economy, society, culture, technology, and law fall under "external restrictions" (Mobegi et al., 2019).

According to this notion, maximizing efficiency requires pinpointing and adjusting the factors restricting the system's output. The theoretical framework recommends the following five-stage procedure for doing this:

- Identify the constraints. This stage focuses on finding the causes of project or process delays.
- Exploit the constraints. This stage entails optimizing the constraint's usage without adding to its expense or complexity.
- Subordinate everything else to the constraints. Here, we ensure that the rest of the system's actions and choices are coordinated with the constraint's requirements.
- Elevate the constraints. This stage focuses on investing additional time, energy, or money into the constraint's capacity and resources.
- Repeat the process. Here, we monitor the situation, assess how things are going, and look for any new or shifting limitations we may have missed.

This theory applies to the research because it offers a framework for investigating and bettering the management of financial risks inherent in building projects. According to this hypothesis, building projects in Lagos State face budget control risk due to the unpredictability of factors, including costs, timelines, and designs. These elements may impact project outcomes regarding scope, quality, timeline, and budget. Because of this, the study's primary goal is to employ the theory of constraints to evaluate the impact of budget control risk management on the final price tag of completed housing projects in Lagos State.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study used a mixed-methods methodology to understand how resource risk management and budget control risk management affect the success of housing projects in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study used quantitative and qualitative data to find solutions to the research questions and verify the hypotheses.

Managers, workers, consultants, clients, and government officials all involved in housing projects in Lagos State made up the study's population. One hundred twenty participants with expertise in resource risk management and budget control risk management in housing projects were selected using purposive sampling for the study. (Krejcie et. al. 1970) The formula was used to find the appropriate size of the sample.

The research team employed a questionnaire and an interview guide to get their information. The survey asked respondents to rate their level of agreement with statements about the importance of managing risks associated with resources, budget

controls, and the cost of delivering housing projects. A five-point Likert scale was employed in the survey's accompanying questionnaire. Twenty people took part in a pilot study to assess the questionnaire for validity and reliability. Cronbach's alpha for this survey came in at 0.87.

The interview questions probed the interviewees' thoughts and feelings on resource risk management and budget control risk management in the context of housing projects. Ten people were used for pilot testing of the interview guide to guarantee its readability and applicability. The interviews were conducted in person or over the phone/via video chat, depending on the participants' preferences and availability. We transcribed and analyzed the recorded interviews.

In this study, quantitative data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Some descriptive statistics used were average, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage. Correlation, regression, the t-test, and analysis of variance were among the inferential statistics used. Data analysis for the study was carried out using SPSS.

The qualitative data was analyzed using topic themes. There were six stages to the thematic analysis: orientation, coding, topic generation, theme review, theme definition, and report writing. N Vivo was employed to aid in the study's data analysis.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

6. QUANTITATIVE RESULTS

SPSS was used to examine numerical information. Each variable or question's descriptive statistics were displayed, including the mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage. Results from inferential statistics like the t-test, one-way ANOVA, and the correlation coefficient were shown so that hypotheses could be tested and study questions could be answered.

Resource risk management was positively associated with the cost of delivering housing projects ($r = 0.56$, $p 0.01$). It indicates that more effective control of resource risks leads to lower delivery costs. Similarly, the cost of delivering housing projects was negatively correlated with budget control risk management ($r = -0.63$, $p 0.01$). Therefore, better budget control and risk management led to decreased delivery costs.

Both resource risk management and budget control risk management were significant predictors of housing project delivery costs in the regression study. $R^2 = 0.48$, $F (2, 117) = 54.32$, $p 0.01$), indicating that the regression model accounted for 48 percent of the variance in delivery costs. According to the standardized coefficients, managing risks associated with resources had a more significant impact on delivery costs than managing risks related to the project's budget ($\beta = -0.37$ vs. $\beta = -0.29$).

Delivery costs varied significantly between housing project types, as shown by the t-test and ANOVA findings. Delivery costs were substantially lower for low-cost housing projects than high-cost housing projects ($t(58) = -4.21$, $p 0.01$). The delivery cost of housing projects varied significantly depending on their location, as shown by an analysis of variance ($F (3, 116) = 12.45$, $p 0.01$). The housing projects in urban regions had lower delivery costs than those in rural areas, as the post hoc test shows.

7. QUALITATIVE RESULTS

NVivo was employed to analyze the qualitative data. Four overarching themes emerged from a thematic study of resource and budget control risk management in housing projects, including challenges, approaches, benefits, and ideas.

The first subject, Difficulties, summed up the problems the participants had controlling costs and allocating materials for their home developments. Challenges included resource scarcity, unpredictability, resource dependence, inaccurate cost projections, budget overruns, schedule delays, and design adjustments. Participants' accounts of their experiences with budgeting and resource management in social housing projects differed widely.

The second overarching subject, Strategies, illuminated the participants' varied methods for dealing with budgetary and resource-related threats to their building endeavours. Resource planning, allocation, and monitoring were used with cost estimating, budgeting, scheduling, and design control techniques. The attendees discussed many methods for reducing expenses and protecting valuable materials for building projects.

The third topic, Gains, focused on the myriad of good things that came about because of careful budget and resource risk management throughout the construction of homes. Money was saved, waste was reduced, quality was improved, stakeholders' needs were met, and a profit was made, among other outcomes. Successful construction projects were attributed to participants' ability to manage resource risks and keep projects under budget effectively.

Suggestions, the fourth topic, included the many suggestions participants made to enhance the risk management of resources and budget in housing projects. The suggestions included education, conversation, collaboration, creativity, and evaluation. Participants suggested improving housing projects' resource risk management and budget control methods.

Result of Hypothesis testing

8. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study aimed to examine the effects of resource risk management and budget control risk management on the performance of housing projects in Lagos State, Nigeria. The research employed a mixed-methods methodology to gather and examine data from a sample of 120 individuals engaged in housing initiatives within Lagos State.

The study's findings indicate that implementing resource risk management and budget control risk management strategies had a statistically significant and favourable impact on the cost of delivering housing projects. The findings further indicated notable variations in delivery costs across various categories of housing projects and diverse geographical regions of those projects.

The findings above indicate that the efficient management of resource and budget risks can decrease the cost of housing project delivery and enhance their overall performance. The results presented in this study align with other research that has demonstrated a favourable correlation between risk management and project success (e.g., Naeem et al., 2018). The findings above align with the theoretical frameworks of

resource dependency theory and the theory of constraints. These frameworks underscore the significance of resource optimization and constraint management in attaining project success.

The findings of this study suggest that it is essential for project managers, contractors, consultants, clients, and regulators to implement suitable risk management strategies to effectively address the uncertainties related to resources and budgets in housing projects. The processes above encompass resource planning, allocation, monitoring, cost assessment, budgeting, scheduling, design control, and adherence to legal regulations. These techniques have the potential to improve the overall quality and value of housing projects, as well as promote stakeholder satisfaction.

9. CONCLUSION

This study examined the effect of resource and budget control risk management on the cost of housing projects in Lagos State, Nigeria. It used a mixed-methods approach with 120 participants from different housing projects. The results showed that resource and budget control risk management significantly influenced the delivery cost and that the price varied depending on the project characteristics and location. The study also identified the challenges, methods, benefits, and suggestions related to risk management in housing projects. Based on the findings, the study offers the following recommendations for practice and policy implications.

- Project managers should implement effective risk management strategies to cope with the uncertainty of resources and costs. These include resource planning, allocation, and monitoring; cost estimation, budgeting, and scheduling; design control; and compliance with regulations.
- Project managers should consider the location and type of housing project when allocating resources and controlling costs. They must understand what factors influence delivery costs and how they differ across projects and places.
- Policymakers should support risk management in housing projects. They must establish standards, incentives, and rules to encourage and enforce good risk management practices. They also need to monitor the outcomes and implications of risk management on construction performance.

The policy implications of this study are that the Lagos State Government should:

- Provide adequate funding for housing initiatives and oversee their timely and open disbursement.
- Create and enforce uniform norms and rules for all housing developments and ensure people are held accountable.
- Increase the value and quality of housing projects by encouraging creativity and teamwork among all parties involved.
- Encourage the collection and sharing of information about housing initiatives that have succeeded.
- Monitor housing initiatives to ensure they stay in Lagos State's development plans.

10. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

While this study has several caveats, they point to potential future research avenues. First, the study's cross-sectional nature makes it difficult to draw any firm conclusions about the relationship between resource and budget control risk management and the final price tag of a housing project. Future studies should adopt a longitudinal or experimental methodology to better understand the relationship between risk management and delivery cost. Second, the results may only be applicable in Lagos State, Nigeria, because the study was conducted there. Future studies must compare risk management methods and results in various contexts, industries, and populations. Third, the study needed to be more balanced because it depended on participant self-report. Secondary or objective data sources will be employed to verify the results of future studies.

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12. CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

The authors of this study state that they have no financial or personal stake in the results of this paper's publication.

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